
A Manifold View of Deep Learning

Hujun Yin

Professor of Artificial Intelligence and Turing Fellow

School of Engineering

The University of Manchester

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Recent Press on AI

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AI

Boom or bubble: what you need to know about investing in AI

Are shares in the tech a smart buy or a giant leap into the unknown, asks David Bentley

It is hard to disagree that AI is a new public utility — one that is essential to the way we live and work. It is also a new public utility that is being built by a handful of companies, and it is being built in a way that is not unlike the way that the internet was built in the 1990s.

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AI boom

Analysts expect growth to be strong in the three months to July

The first three months of 2024, according to the data provider Statista, have seen a boom in AI-related stocks. In the first three months of 2024, the AI boom investment index rose 26 per cent, compared with a 13 per cent rise in the S&P 500. The index is up 100 per cent since its launch in January 2023.

For the first time since 2015, according to the data provider Statista, the AI boom investment index has outperformed the S&P 500. In the first three months of 2024, the AI boom investment index rose 26 per cent, compared with a 13 per cent rise in the S&P 500.

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New Challenges:

- Energy
- Sustainability
- Net-zero
- Manufacturing
- Agriculture
- Materials

with 10% of the revenues that were a long time ago. It is back to the future, says a leading analyst. The AI boom is not a bubble, but a new era of growth.

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Companies with AI related activities have 25% gains compared to 5% of those without AI. AI is now regarded as the ability to think and learn as a modern company.

Nvidia shares up by 76% since 1 Jan 2023, fuelled by the boom of AI/DL developments with sales forecast of \$11 bn 3 months to July.

AI boom is compared with dot.com boom.

Build your wealth with confidence

Manifold

Topology Set **Mannigfaltigkeit**

Neighbourhood 流形

Topological space

Manifold Tensor chart

Metric space

Riemannian manifold

Differential geometry

In Bernhard Riemann - - duality reduction

from L. Tu "An Introduction to Manifolds" visualisation

Manifold

*“So far as the laws of mathematics refer to reality, they are not certain.
And so far as they are certain, they do not refer to reality.”* Albert Einstein

Manifold

Manifold is a topological space that is locally Euclidean

Y. Bengio, I Goodfellow, A. Courville

The “*Deep Learning Book*”, 2015 version

- *Manifold learning is an approach to machine learning that is capitalizing on the manifold hypothesis: data generating distribution to concentrate near regions of low dimensionality.*
- *The use of the term manifold in machine learning is much looser than its use in mathematics: (i) data may not be strictly on the manifold, but only near it; (ii) the dimensionality may not be the same everywhere; (iii) the notion actually referred to in machine learning naturally extends to discrete spaces.*

Manifold

Manifold is a topological space that is locally Euclidean

- Patent
WO2018185462A1

(Yin, Burnstone, Zaki,
11 October 2018)

- Video synthesis
(Peng, Zaki & Yin 2017)

Y. Bengio, I Goodfellow, A. Courville
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AI/ML/NNs/DL

the context

While statistical ML methods such as logistic regression, PCA, SVMs, kernel methods, mixture models are still widely used, neural networks, inc, convolutional neural networks or deep networks, are dominating in many data-driven applications. NNs are approximators that learn and quantify uncertainties and data representations.

(Artificial) Neural Networks

“The measure of intelligence is the ability to change.” Albert Einstein

$$J = \frac{1}{2} E[e^2(t)]$$

$$J(t) = \frac{1}{2} e^2(t)$$

$$\frac{\partial J(t)}{\partial \mathbf{w}} = e(t) \frac{\partial e(t)}{\partial \mathbf{w}} = -\mathbf{x}(t)e(t)$$

$$\mathbf{w}(t+1) = \mathbf{w}(t) - \alpha \frac{\partial J(t)}{\partial \mathbf{w}} = \mathbf{w}(t) + \alpha \mathbf{x}(t)e(t) = \mathbf{w}(t) + \alpha \mathbf{x}(t)[d(t) - \mathbf{x}(t)^T \mathbf{w}(t)]$$

$$b(t+1) = b(t) + \alpha [d(t) - \mathbf{x}(t)^T \mathbf{w}(t)]$$

Hard limit function

$$\phi(v) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } v > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Sigmoid function

$$\phi(v) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-v}}$$

Neural Networks

The **Back-Propagation algorithm** (Rumhart, Hinton & Williams 1986)

- Step 1: *Initialisation*. Set all weights and nodes' biases to small random numbers.
- Step 2: *Presentation of training examples*. input $\mathbf{x}=[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]^T$, n is number of input variables and desired output $\mathbf{d}=[d_1, d_2, \dots, d_m]^T$, m is the number of output nodes.
- Step 3: **Forward computation**. Calculate the outputs of the hidden and output nodes,

$$y_k = \varphi_k^o \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n_h} w_{jk}^o v_j + b_k^o \right) \quad v_j = \varphi_j^h \left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_{ij}^h x_i + b_j^h \right)$$

- Step 4: **Backward computation and weights updating**. Compute the error terms,

$$\delta_k^o = e_k^o (\varphi_k^o)' = e_k^o y_k (1 - y_k) = y_k (1 - y_k) (d_k - y_k)$$

$$\delta_j^h = (\varphi_j^h)' \sum_{k=1}^m \delta_k^o w_{jk}^o = v_j (1 - v_j) \sum_{k=1}^m \delta_k^o w_{jk}^o$$

$$w_{jk}^o = w_{jk}^o + \alpha \delta_k^o v_j$$

$$w_{ij}^h = w_{ij}^h + \alpha \delta_j^h x_i$$

$b_j \dots$

- Step 5: *Iteration*. Repeat steps 3 and 4 and stop when the total error reaches the required level).

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)

- *feature layer* (convolutional filters)
- *pooling/subsampling layer* (summarise or select responses of the filters, e.g. mean or max pooling)

CNN LeNet5 Architecture (LeCun & Bottou 1998)

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)

- **Typical CNNs:** AlexNet, VGG16, GoogLeNet, ResNet, GANs, ...

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)

- Performances

Top-5 error rates in the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge.
Source: <https://devblogs.nvidia.com/mocha-jl-deep-learning-julia/>

Although CNNs are reported to have outperformed humans in many image classification tasks, there are still performance gaps when deploying CNN models in real-world applications.

However, CNNs or deep learning are maturing as more complete learning systems rather than just the core classifiers. Modern deep learning further injects physics models and data structures to make the learning more traceable and less reliant on huge amount of real data.

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Manifold: from PCA to Autoencoder

- Autoassociative Neural Networks (**Kramer, AIChE, 1991**)

PCA

$$\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{Y}$$

Y: data matrix

V: eigenvector matrix

T: principal components

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{T}$$

Y: reconstruction

$$\min E(\mathbf{Y} - \hat{\mathbf{Y}})$$

Via

back-propagation

self-supervised learning

Layer 1 2 3 4 5
input mapping bottleneck demapping output
layer layer layer layer layer

Manifold: Autoencoder

- Deep Autoencoder (**Hinton & Salakhutdinov, *Science*, 2006**)

Variational Autoencoder (VAE)

- VAEs (Kingma & Welling, 2014, 2015)

$$l_i(\theta, \phi) = -E_{z \sim q_\theta(z|x_i)}[\log p_\phi(x_i|z)] + KL(q_\theta(z|x_i) || p(z))$$

← low-dimensional/latent space is stochastic

Generative Adversarial Networks

- GANs (Goodfellow, et al, 2014)

$$\min_G \max_D V(D, G) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \sim p_{\text{data}}(\mathbf{x})} [\log D(\mathbf{x})] + \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{z} \sim p_{\mathbf{z}}(\mathbf{z})} [\log(1 - D(G(\mathbf{z})))]$$

Algorithm 1 Minibatch stochastic gradient descent training of generative adversarial nets. The number of steps to apply to the discriminator, k , is a hyperparameter. We used $k = 1$, the least expensive option, in our experiments.

for number of training iterations **do**

for k steps **do**

- Sample minibatch of m noise samples $\{\mathbf{z}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{(m)}\}$ from noise prior $p_g(\mathbf{z})$.
- Sample minibatch of m examples $\{\mathbf{x}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{x}^{(m)}\}$ from data generating distribution $p_{\text{data}}(\mathbf{x})$.
- Update the discriminator by ascending its stochastic gradient:

$$\nabla_{\theta_d} \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m [\log D(\mathbf{x}^{(i)}) + \log(1 - D(G(\mathbf{z}^{(i)})))]$$

end for

- Sample minibatch of m noise samples $\{\mathbf{z}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{(m)}\}$ from noise prior $p_g(\mathbf{z})$.
- Update the generator by descending its stochastic gradient:

$$\nabla_{\theta_g} \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \log(1 - D(G(\mathbf{z}^{(i)})))$$

end for

The gradient-based updates can use any standard gradient-based learning rule. We used momentum in our experiments.

Generative Adversarial Networks

- Applications

CycleGAN, Zhu et al 2017

Monet ↔ Photos

Zebra ↔ Horse

Summer ↔ Winter

Monet → photo

photo → Monet

zebra → horse

horse → zebra

summer → winter

winter → summer

Photograph → Monet → Van Gogh → Cezanne → Ukiyo-e

- **ApprGAN (Peng & Yin, Neurocomputing 2019), Manifold-enhanced CycleGAN (Huang & Yin, Imaging Science Journal, 2022)**

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{full}(G_{X \rightarrow Y}, G_{Y \rightarrow X}, D_X, D_Y) = & \mathcal{L}_{GAN}(G_{X \rightarrow Y}, D_Y, X, Y) \\ & + \mathcal{L}_{GAN}(G_{Y \rightarrow X}, D_X, X, Y) \\ & + \lambda_1 \mathcal{L}_{rec}(G_{X \rightarrow Y}, G_{Y \rightarrow X}) \\ & + \lambda_2 \mathcal{L}_{id}(G_{X \rightarrow Y}, G_{Y \rightarrow X}), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 are ratios controlling the balance between these three terms. Generators $G_{X \rightarrow Y}$, $G_{Y \rightarrow X}$ and discriminators D_X , D_Y are trained by solving

$$\arg \min_{(G_{X \rightarrow Y}, G_{Y \rightarrow X})} \max_{(D_X, D_Y)} \mathcal{L}_{full}(G_{X \rightarrow Y}, G_{Y \rightarrow X}, D_X, D_Y). \quad (5)$$

- Caricature Style Modelling and Synthesis (Huo, et al., IEEE Trans on Image Processing, 2022)

- MRF-based and generated deep features (**Peng, Hankins and Yin, Neurocomputing, 2018**)

CIFAR10

SOMNet

1st layer

2nd layer

Manifold

Benefits:

- *help build more meaningful, topological feature spaces*
- *help quantify variations of features*
- *help explain roles of feature spaces in yielding final output*
- *help build associations between feature spaces of different modalities*

Thank you !